

FORMATION OF CREATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN OF JUNIOR AGE

¹Akhmatkhonova A.B., ²Melibayeva R.N.

¹Tashkent Puchon University. 1st year master's student in the field of management in education

²Scientific supervisor: ph.d.p.s. (PhD)

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Abstract. *Consideration of the problem of development of abilities for psychological and pedagogical research has been and remains relevant up to the present day. Development of creative abilities of children has attracted the attention of representatives of various fields of scientific knowledge for many years – philosophy, psychology, pedagogy and others. Modern society needs active individuals who are able to quickly respond to changes and find quality solutions to problematic situations. There is also increased attention to the inner world and unique capabilities of each individual. The peculiarity of this type of thinking is that in order to solve a problem, a person does not concentrate all efforts on finding one possible solution, but looks for solutions by going through all the options in order to analyze as many results as possible.*

Keywords: *development of abilities, development, creative abilities of children, pedagogy, psychology, training, education, primary school age.*

The main aspects of studying creative abilities in psychological and pedagogical science are the psychological basis of heuristic learning, scientific ideas about the nature of students' creativity, in connection with which, the need to understand and manage the nature of the creative process arose as a consequence of the need for controlled influence and maintenance of creative activity in an up-to-date state, increasing its effectiveness.

In modern pedagogy and psychology, there is an intensification of research in the field of psychology of creativity, since the practical activities of teachers in various fields of activity have confirmed scientific research in the aspect: creative achievements have not only a personal character, but also a social one.

In modern science, a separate direction has developed that studies the problems of creativity and creative activity: the psychology of creativity (E.P. Ilyin, 2009; G. Revesh, 1999). The main task of the psychology of creativity is to reveal the mental patterns and mechanisms of the creative process and creativity [4].

Foreign researchers consider creativity as the basis and mechanism for the development of the psyche (A.M. Matyushkin, Ya.A. Ponomarev, I.N. Semenov, etc.), while scientific research in this area is associated with the laws of thinking (V.S. Bibler, O.K. Tikhomirov, E.G. Yudin).

The following foreign scientists conducted research into the psychology of creativity: J. Guilford, W. Smith, E. Torrance, D. Halpern, and others. However, as noted by the authors Ya. A. Ponomarev, E. G. Yudin, M. G. Yaroshevsky, the studies of creativity were not sufficiently effective (A. S. Belkin, 2000). Most researchers focus on the characteristics or qualities of personality in defining creativity. Thus, J. Guilford believes that creativity and creative potential can be defined as a set of abilities and other traits that contribute to successful creative thinking (N. I. Chernetskaya, 2014; M. G. Yaroshevsky, 2006) [6].

In general, two main groups of approaches to the study of the problem of creativity can be distinguished: - studies of general psychological and conceptual orientation (S.L. Rubinstein,

1989; D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya, 1983; Ya.A. Ponomarev, 1976; O.K. Tikhomirov, 1969), which substantiated the foundations of the psychology of creativity, its patterns and mechanisms of creative implementation; - experimental and empirical studies of creativity of the differential psychological type, aimed at identifying, describing, and systematizing personal characteristics and abilities for creative activity[5].

One of the most pressing problems of modern psychological and pedagogical science is the creation of a general psychological and pedagogical theory of creativity (B.F. Lomov, Ya.A. Ponomarev, O.K. Tikhomirov) (L.S. Vygotsky, 1991). In modern domestic and foreign psychology of creativity in the aspect of the subject-process level, the idea of the stages of the creative process dominates: emergence of a problem, incubation stage, insight, formalization of an idea, verification. The key element is considered to be the intuitive stage (A.V. Brushlinsky, Ya.A. Ponomarev, R. Wallace, etc.) (L.S. Bushueva, 2014). E. Torrens defines creativity as the emergence of a special sensitivity to problems associated with a lack of knowledge, identification of difficulties, the process of generating assumptions and forming hypotheses (A.G. Bermus, 2004). A number of scientists (V.P. Kartsev, M.G. Yaroshevsky) conduct research in the social aspect of creativity: at the socio-psychological and socio-managerial levels - the determinants of creativity [7].

Around the psychology of creativity and the group, related psychological sciences, many applied disciplines have developed, linking psychology with pedagogical and other similar sciences, and through them with practice (L.S. Bushueva, 2014). Thus, new conceptual approaches to creativity allow us to say that this category is multidimensional, requiring a systemic approach. From our point of view, creativity is the basis of innovative education.

In modern psychological and pedagogical science, creativity is considered as a personal category in the aspects of: manifestations of divergent thinking; actualization of intellectual activity [11].

Following the position of scientists who define creative abilities as an independent factor, the development of which is the result of teaching creative activity to primary school students, we will highlight the components of creative abilities of primary school students: - creative thinking, - creative imagination, - the use of methods for organizing creative activity. To develop creative thinking and creative imagination of primary school students, it is necessary to offer the following tasks: - classify objects, situations, phenomena on various grounds; - establish cause-and-effect relationships; - see interrelations and identify new connections between systems; - consider a system in development; - make predictions; - highlight opposing features of an object; - identify and form contradictions; - separate contradictory properties of objects in space and time; - imagine spatial objects (L.V. Kuznetsova, 2008) [9].

Creative tasks are differentiated by such parameters as the complexity of the problem situations they contain, the complexity of the mental operations required to solve them, and the forms of presenting contradictions (explicit, hidden). In this regard, three levels of complexity of the content of the creative task system are distinguished. Tasks of the III (initial) level of complexity are presented to first- and second-grade students. A specific object, phenomenon, or human resource acts as an object at this level. Creative tasks of this level contain a problematic question or a problematic situation, involve the use of the method of enumerating options or heuristic methods of creativity and are intended to develop creative intuition and spatial productive imagination.

Tasks of the II level of complexity are one step lower and are aimed at developing the basics of systemic thinking, productive imagination, and mainly algorithmic methods of creativity. The object in tasks of this level is the concept of "system", as well as system resources. They are presented in the form of a vague problem situation or contain contradictions in an explicit form. The goal of tasks of this type is to develop the basics of students' systemic thinking.

Tasks of the I (highest, high, advanced) level of complexity. These are open tasks from various fields of knowledge, containing hidden contradictions. The objects are considered to be biosystems, polysystems, and resources of any systems. Tasks of this type are offered to students in the third and fourth years of study. They are aimed at developing the basics of dialectical thinking, controlled imagination, and conscious application of algorithmic and heuristic methods of creativity. The methods of creativity chosen by students when completing tasks characterize the corresponding levels of development of creative thinking and creative imagination.

Thus, the transition to a new level of development of creative abilities of primary school students occurs in the process of accumulation of creative activity by each student (I. Shvantsara, 1978). Level III – involves the execution of tasks based on the enumeration of options and accumulated creative experience in preschool age and heuristic methods. The following creative methods are used: - focal object method; - morphological analysis; - control question method; - individual typical fantasy techniques. Level II - involves performing creative tasks based on heuristic methods and elements of the theory of inventive tasks, such as: the little people method, methods for overcoming psychological inertia, system operator, resource approach, laws of system development.

Level I – involves completing creative tasks based on the thinking tools of the theory of inventive problems: – an adapted algorithm for solving inventive problems, – techniques for resolving contradictions in space and time, – typical techniques for resolving contradictions (A.S. Belkin, 2000; S.I. Gin, 2000; E.I. Nikolaeva, 2009). Domestic psychologists and educators (L.I. Aidarova, L.S. Vygotsky, L.V. Zankov, V.V. Davydov, Z.I. Kolmykova, V.A. Krutetsky, D.B. Elkonin and others) emphasize the importance of educational activities for the development of creative thinking, cognitive activity, and the accumulation of subjective experience in students' creative search activities[8].

The experience of creative activity, according to researchers, is an independent structural element of the content of education: - transfer of previously acquired knowledge to a new situation; - independent vision of the problem, alternatives for its solution; - combination of previously acquired methods into new and other ones.

Analysis of the main psychological new formations and the nature of the leading activity of this age period, modern requirements for the organization of training as a creative process, which the student together with the teacher in a certain sense build themselves; orientation at this age to the subject of activity and methods of its transformation presuppose the possibility of accumulating creative experience not only in the process of cognition, but also in such types of activity as the creation and transformation of specific objects, situations, phenomena, creative application of knowledge obtained in the learning process[10].

In the psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue, definitions of creative activities are given. Cognition is "... the educational activity of a student, understood as a process of creative activity that forms their knowledge" (L.S. Bushueva, 2014; S.I. Ozhegov, 2016). In primary school age, for the first time, a division occurs between play and work, that is, activities

carried out for the sake of pleasure that the child will receive in the process of the activity itself and activities aimed at achieving an objectively significant and socially assessed result. This distinction between play and work, including academic work, is an important feature of school age (V.D. Shadrikov, 2014). The importance of imagination in primary school age is the highest and necessary ability of a person. At the same time, it is this ability that requires special care in terms of development. And it develops especially intensively at the age of 5 to 15 years.

And if this period of imagination is not specially developed, then a rapid decrease in the activity of this function occurs (D.B. Elkonin, 1979; D.B. Elkonin, 1989). Along with the decrease in a person's ability to fantasize, the personality becomes impoverished, the possibilities of creative thinking decrease, interest in art, science, etc. fades. Younger schoolchildren carry out most of their active work with the help of imagination. Their games are the fruit of a wild imagination, they are enthusiastically engaged in creative activities. The psychological basis of the latter is also creative imagination. When, in the process of learning, children are faced with the need to comprehend abstract material and they need analogies, support with a general lack of life experience, imagination also comes to the aid of the child.

Thus, the significance of the imagination function in mental development is great (A.S. Belkin, 2000; A.V. Khutorsky, 2000; B.M. Teplov, 1982; E.A. Flerina, 1961). However, fantasy, like any form of mental reflection, must have a positive direction of development. It should contribute to better self-disclosure and self-improvement of the individual through knowledge of the surrounding world, and not develop into passive daydreaming, replacing real life with dreams. To accomplish this task, it is necessary to help the child use his or her imagination in the direction of progressive self-development, to activate the cognitive activity of schoolchildren, in particular the development of theoretical, abstract thinking, attention, speech and creativity in general. Children of primary school age are very fond of artistic creativity. It allows the child to reveal his personality in the most complete free form. All artistic activity is based on active imagination, creative thinking. These functions provide the child with a new, unusual view of the world.

They contribute to the development of thinking, memory, and enrich his individual life experience. According to L.S. Vygotsky, imagination ensures the following activities of a child (V.V. Davydov, 1973; A.N. Mukina, 2007): - construction of an image, the final result of his activity, - creation of a program of behavior in a situation of uncertainty, creation of images replacing activity, - creation of images of described objects. Thus, drawing a conclusion on the paragraph, it should be noted that the formation of many interests is very important for the development of the child. A schoolchild is generally characterized by a cognitive attitude to the world. Such a curious orientation has an objective expediency. Interest in everything expands the child's life experience, introduces him to different types of activity, activates his various abilities.

The emergence of the game method is associated with the requirements for increasing the effectiveness of training through more active involvement of students in the process of not only obtaining, but also directly (here and now) using knowledge. The game method is multi-purpose, as it provides teachers and students with ample opportunities to express their creativity. Game methods allow using all levels of knowledge acquisition: from reproductive activity through transformative to the main goal – creative and search activity. Creative and search activity is more effective if it is preceded by reproducing and transforming activity, during which students learn learning techniques (N.P. Anikeeva, 2009). The place and role of game methods in the educational

process, the combination of elements of play and learning largely depend on the teacher's understanding of the functions and classification of pedagogical games [6].

In preschool and primary school age, three classes of games are distinguished: - games that arise on the initiative of the child - amateur games; □ games that arise on the initiative of an adult, introducing them for educational and upbringing purposes; □ games that come from the historically established traditions of an ethnic group - folk games; □ games that can arise both on the initiative of an adult and older children. Each of the listed classes of games, in turn, is represented by types and subtypes. Thus, the first class includes: experimentation games and plot amateur games - plot-educational, plot-role, director's and theatrical. This class of games seems to be the most productive for the development of intellectual initiative, creativity of the child, which is manifested in setting new game tasks for themselves and other players; for the emergence of new motives and types of activity.

It is the games that arise on the initiative of the children themselves that most vividly represent the game as a form of practical reflection on the material of knowledge about the surrounding reality of significant experiences and impressions associated with the child's life experience. It is the independent game that is the leading activity in preschool childhood. The content of amateur games is "fed" by the experience of other types of child activity and meaningful communication with adults. The second class of games includes educational games (didactic, plot-didactic and others) and leisure games, which include fun games, entertainment games, intellectual games. All games can be independent, but they are never amateur, since independence in them is based on learning the rules, and not on the child's initial initiative in setting the game task. The educational and developmental value of such games is enormous [7].

They form a culture of play; promote the assimilation of social norms and rules; and, most importantly, are, along with other types of activity, the basis for amateur games in which children can creatively use the knowledge they have acquired. Didactic games are a type of games with rules, specially created by a pedagogical school for the purpose of teaching and educating children. Didactic games are aimed at solving specific problems in teaching children, but at the same time, they have an educational and developmental influence of gaming activities.

The use of didactic games as a means of teaching younger students is determined by a number of reasons: 1) play activity as the leading one in preschool childhood has not yet lost its significance in primary school age, therefore reliance on play activity, play forms and techniques is the most adequate way of involving children in educational work; 2) mastering educational activity, involving children in it is slow; 3) there are age-related characteristics of children associated with insufficient stability and arbitrariness of attention, predominantly voluntary development of memory, predominance of visual-figurative type of thinking; 4) cognitive motivation is insufficiently formed.

The motive and content of educational activity do not correspond to each other. There are significant difficulties in adaptation when entering school. Didactic game largely contributes to overcoming the above difficulties. Didactic game has a certain structure, characterizing the game as a form of learning and game activity. The following structural components of a didactic game are distinguished: 1) didactic task; 2) game actions; 3) game rules; 4) result. The didactic task is determined by the purpose of training and educational influence. It is formed by the teacher and reflects his educational activity. For example, in a number of didactic games, in accordance with the program tasks of the corresponding subjects, the ability to form words from letters is

reinforced, and counting skills are practiced. The game task is carried out by children. The didactic task in the didactic game is realized through the game task. It determines the game actions, becomes the task of the child himself [5].

Game actions are the basis of the game. The more varied the game actions are, the more interesting the game itself is for children and the more successfully the cognitive and game tasks are solved. In different games, game actions differ in their focus and in relation to the players. These are, for example, role-playing actions, guessing riddles, spatial transformations, etc. They are connected with the game concept and proceed from it. Game actions are the means of implementing the game concept, but also include actions aimed at fulfilling the didactic task.

Game rules. Their content and direction are determined by the general tasks of forming the child's personality, cognitive content, game tasks and game actions. In a didactic game, the rules are given. With the help of rules, the teacher controls the game, the processes of cognitive activity, and the behavior of children. The rules also influence the solution of the didactic task - they imperceptibly limit the actions of children, direct their attention to the fulfillment of a specific task of the subject. Summing up - the result is summed up immediately after the end of the game. This may be scoring; identifying children who have completed the game task better; determining the winning team, etc. At the same time, it is necessary to note the achievements of each child, emphasize the successes of lagging children (A.K. Bondarenko, 2012). When conducting games, it is necessary to preserve all structural elements. Since it is with their help that didactic tasks are solved [9].

The relationship between children and the teacher is determined not by the learning situation, but by the game. Children and the teacher are participants in the same game. This condition is violated, and the teacher takes the path of direct teaching. Thus, a didactic game is a game only for a child, and for an adult it is a way of learning. The goal of didactic games is to facilitate the transition to learning tasks, to make it gradual. From the above, we can formulate the main functions of didactic games: - the function of forming a stable interest in learning and relieving stress; - associated with the process of the child's adaptation to the school regime;- the function of forming mental neoplasms; -the function of forming educational activity itself; - the function of forming general educational skills, skills of independent educational work; - the function of forming self-control and self-assessment skills; - the function of forming adequate relationships and mastering social roles. Thus, a didactic game is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon.

The following conditions are necessary for organizing and conducting a didactic game: - the teacher must have certain knowledge and skills regarding didactic games; -expressiveness of the game; - the need to include the teacher in the game; - an optimal combination of entertainment and learning; - means and methods that increase children's emotional attitude to the game should be considered not as an end in itself, but as a path leading to the fulfillment of didactic tasks; - the visual aids used in a didactic game must be simple, accessible and capacious. All educational games can be divided into three main types: 1 – games with objects (toys, natural materials); 2 – board games; 3 – word games. In games with objects, toys and real objects are used. Playing with them, children learn to compare, establish similarities and differences between objects. The value of these games is that with their help, children become familiar with the properties of objects and their characteristics: color, size, shape, quality.

The games solve problems on comparison, classification, establishing a sequence in solving problems. As children acquire new knowledge about the subject environment, the tasks in the games become more complex: younger students practice identifying an object by one quality, combine objects by this feature (color, shape, quality, purpose), which is very important for the development of abstract, logical thinking. The game also uses objects in which the difference between them is less noticeable. In games with objects, younger students perform tasks that require conscious memorization of the number and location of objects, finding a missing object [12].

Thus, it is important for teachers to think through the phased distribution of games, including didactic ones, in the lesson. At the beginning of the lesson, the goal of the game is to organize and interest children, to stimulate their activity. In the middle of the lesson, the didactic game should solve the problem of mastering the topic. At the end of the lesson, the game can be of a search nature. At any stage of the lesson, the game must meet the following requirements: be interesting, accessible, exciting, involve children in different types of activities. Consequently, the game can be conducted at any stage of the lesson, as well as in lessons of different types. The game is part of the holistic pedagogical process, combined and interconnected with other forms of teaching and education of primary school students.

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